

Some New Schiff Base Derivatives Derived from Vanillin as Possible Fungicides

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Manuscript received 19 August 1982, accepted 30 May 1983

A new series of Schiff bases derived from 4-substituted and 4,5-disubstituted-2-amino thiazoles and vanillin was synthesised. Cycloaddition of Schiff bases with thioglycollic acid yielded thiazolidone derivatives. Condensation of the Schiff bases with chloroacetyl chloride and subsequent reaction with piperidine and morpholine yielded corresponding acetoxy derivatives. The compounds were characterised by elemental analysis and ir spectra. They were also screened for their fungicidal activity.

SCHIFF bases are well known to have pronounced biological activities¹⁻⁹. Their ready synthesis and myriad properties have contributed greatly to their popularity and to the study of many biological systems. Schiff base complexes have been suggested as models for enzymes such as galactose oxidase¹⁰. Schiff bases and their metal complexes derived from thiazole amines have been reported^{9,11} from this laboratory. In the present investigation, the synthesis of a new series of Schiff bases derived from 4-substituted and 4,5-disubstituted-2-amino thiazoles and vanillin has been undertaken. Cycloaddition of thioglycollic acid with the Schiff bases yielded thiazolidone derivatives. Condensation of the Schiff bases with chloroacetyl chloride and subsequent reaction with piperidine and morpholine yielded corresponding piperidino acetoxy and morpholino acetoxy derivatives. The steps involved in the synthesis are sketched in Scheme 1. The compounds have been characterised by their sharp m.p., elemental analysis and ir spectra. The ir spectra of Schiff bases showed a broad medium band around 3100 cm^{-1} (bonded OH) and a strong sharp band in the region 1640-1625 cm^{-1} (C=N). On thiazolidone formation, the band due to C=N stretching is lost

and a strong tertiary amide stretch ($\text{>N}-\text{C}=\text{O}$) is observed around 1680 cm^{-1} . Disappearance of the OH band and appearance of a new band around 1715-1725 cm^{-1} established the formation of the acetoxy derivatives.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. IR spectra in KBr were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 grating Infrared spectrophotometer.

4-Aryl-2-amino thiazoles were prepared by the condensation of substituted acetophenones with thiourea in presence of iodine¹².

4,5-Diaryl-2-amino thiazoles: 4,5-Diaryl-2-amino thiazoles were prepared from respective desyl

chlorides. Benzoin or substituted benzoin was treated with thionyl chloride to form the corresponding desyl chloride¹³. A mixture of desyl chloride (1 mole) and thiourea (1 mole) was refluxed in absolute ethanol on water bath for 6 hr. The excess of solvent was evaporated. The product obtained was cooled and made alkaline with dil. NH_4OH . The solid separated was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol.

4',5'-Di(o-chlorophenyl)thiazole-2'-imino(3-methoxy-4-hydroxy)benzylidene : A mixture of 2-amino-4,5-di(o-chlorophenyl)thiazole (0.01 mole), vanillin (0.01 mole) in ethanol (30 ml) and piperidine (3-4 drops) was refluxed on water bath for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid separated was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 125°, yield 70%. (Found : C, 60.52 ; H, 3.28 ; N, 6.03. $C_{23}H_{16}N_2O_2SCl_2$ requires C, 60.78 ; H, 3.52 ; N, 6.17%). Other substituted thiazole imino(3-methoxy-4-hydroxy)benzylidenes were prepared in a similar manner. Melting points, yield and antifungal activity are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	% Inhibition of <i>Curvularia</i> at 500 ppm
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	H	158	84.7
2.	-p-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	152	87.2
3.	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	H	135	90.1
4.	-p-Br-C ₆ H ₄	H	165	90.7
5.	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	180	89.2
6.	α-Naphthyl	H	178	92.4
7.	-C ₆ H ₅	-C ₆ H ₅	170	85.1
8.	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	185	90.5
9.	-o-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-o-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	125	91.4
10.	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	115	91.6

Elemental analysis (C, H, N) were within ±0.5% of the theoretical values. The yields are in between 60-75%.

4',5'-Di(o-chlorophenyl)thiazole-2'-imino(3-methoxy-4-chloroacetoxy)benzylidene : A mixture of 4',5'-di(o-chlorophenyl)thiazole-2'-imino(3-methoxy-4-hydroxy)benzylidene (0.01 mole), chloroacetyl chloride (0.015 mole) in dry benzene (15-20 ml) with pyridine (2 to 3 drops) was refluxed on water bath for 5 hr. The excess of benzene and pyridine were removed under reduced pressure. The residue was washed thoroughly with water and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 118°, yield 60%. (Found : N, 5.18 ; Cl, 19.95. $C_{24}H_{17}N_2O_3SCl_3$ requires N, 5.26 ; Cl, 20.09%). Other substituted thiazole-imino(3-methoxy-4-chloroacetoxy)benzylidenes were prepared in a similar manner.

4',5'-Di(o-chlorophenyl)thiazole-2'-imino(3-methoxy-4-morpholino acetoxy)benzylidene : A mixture of 4',5'-di(o-chlorophenyl)thiazole-2'-imino(3-methoxy-4-chloroacetoxy)benzylidene (0.005 mole) and morpholine (0.01 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed on water bath for 8 hr. Excess benzene was removed under reduced pressure. The solid mass obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 120°, yield 55%. (Found : C, 60.45 ; H, 4.14 ; N, 7.09. $C_{28}H_{28}N_3O_4SCl_2$ requires C, 59.79 ; H, 4.29 ; N, 7.21%). Other substituted thiazole imino(3-methoxy-4-morpholino/piperidino acetoxy)benzylidenes were prepared in a similar manner. Melting point, % yield and antifungal data are given in Table 2.

2-(4'-Hydroxy-3'-methoxy phenyl)-3-[4'',5''-di(o-chlorophenyl)-thiazol-2''-yl]-4-thiazolidone : A mixture of 4',5'-di(o-chlorophenyl)thiazole-2'-imino(3-

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	R	m.p. °C	% Inhibition of <i>Curvularia</i> at 500 ppm
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	H	-N	98	72.41
2.	-p-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	-do-	125	74.1
3.	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	H	-do-	138	78.6
4.	-p-Br-C ₆ H ₄	H	-do-	175	79.2
5.	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	-do-	103	80.5
6.	α-Naphthyl	H	-do-	212	84.7
7.	-C ₆ H ₅	-C ₆ H ₅	-do-	105	76.4
8.	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	-do-	146	78.2
9.	-o-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-o-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-do-	120	78.6
10.	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-do-	170	79.1
11.	-C ₆ H ₅	H	-N	102	72.8
12.	-p-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	H	-do-	105	74.3
13.	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	H	-do-	>280	78.9
14.	-p-Br-C ₆ H ₄	H	-do-	140	79.3
15.	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	-do-	124	80.3
16.	α-Naphthyl	H	-do-	180	84.9
17.	-C ₆ H ₅	-C ₆ H ₅	-do-	125	75.8
18.	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	-do-	135	78.5
19.	-o-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-o-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-do-	126	78.9
20.	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-do-	164	79.3

Elemental analysis (C, H, N) were within ±0.5% of the theoretical values. The yields are in between 50-65%.

methoxy-4-hydroxy)benzylidene (0.01 mole) and thioglycollic acid (0.015 mole) in dry benzene (30 ml) was refluxed on water bath for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and excess of benzene was removed under reduced pressure. The solid residue obtained was washed several times with NaHCO₃ solution and water and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 141°, yield 65%. (Found : C, 56.35 ; H, 2.66 ; N, 5.41. C₁₂H₁₁N₂O₃S₂Cl₂ requires C, 56.71 ; H, 3.40 ; N, 5.28%). Other thiazolidones of the series were prepared in a similar manner. Melting points, % yield and % inhibition of fungal growth are given in Table 3.

were tested for their toxicity towards *Curvularia* species isolated from diseased rice leaves infected with *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

The compounds were tested at a concentration of 500 ppm for 72 hr. The experiments were performed in duplicate and the average % inhibition is reported (Tables 1-3). From the result of the fungicidal tests it is found that the presence of halogen, α -naphthyl and methoxy group in the compound enhances the fungicidal activity. It is also observed that the Schiff bases are more active than the corresponding thiazolidones and acetoxy derivatives.

TABLE 3

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	% Inhibition of <i>Curvularia</i> at 500 ppm
1.	-C ₆ H ₅	H	185	57.4
2.	-p-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	108	57.6
3.	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	H	154	64.2
4.	-p-Br-C ₆ H ₄	H	115	64.5
5.	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	H	175	62.7
6.	α -Naphthyl	H	180	65.1
7.	-C ₆ H ₅	-C ₆ H ₅	127	58.5
8.	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	-p-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	148	62.9
9.	-o-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-o-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	141	64.7
10.	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	-p-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	138	64.8

Elemental analysis (C, H, N) were within $\pm 0.5\%$ of the theoretical values. The yields are in between 60-65%.

Antifungal activity: For fungicidal assay poisoned food technique¹⁴ was used. All the compounds

References

1. E. M. HODNETT and W. J. DUNN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 768.
2. E. M. HODNETT and P. D. MOONEY, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, **13**, 786.
3. H. J. BILLMANN and R. L. SCHMIDGALL, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1970, **59**, 1191.
4. YUN SUNG CHO, *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **79**, 73990.
5. H. PACHECO, L. CRONENBERGER, D. PILLOU and J. THOLLIERE, *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, **72**, 111001, 111002.
6. E. PROFFT and E. G. HORGEL, *Chem. Abs.*, 1974, **80**, 26913.
7. A. A. SANTILLI, DONG HAN KIN and A. R. FIEBER, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1974, **63**, 449.
8. B. DASH, M. PATRA and S. PRAHARAJ, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **19B**, 894.
9. S. S. TIWARI, M. I. HUSAIN and G. C. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 214.
10. R. S. GIORDANO and R. D. BENEMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 1017, 1023.
11. B. DASH and S. K. MAHAPATRA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1976, **37**, 271.
12. B. DASH and M. K. ROU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 663.
13. L. F. FIEBER, "Experiments in Organic Chemistry", D. C. Heath and Company, Boston, 1957, 3rd. Edn. p. 180.
14. Y. L. NENE, "Fungicidal Plant Disease Control", Oxford and I. B. H. Publishing Company, New Delhi, 1971.